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1 Version History

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0.1	M Vichi, G Fearon, S Dey	Draft submission	26/02/2024
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2 Executive summary

This deliverable describes the main technical features and summary results of the numerical models used for simulating the physics and biogeochemistry of the Southern Benguela Upwelling System. The regional configuration is based on the Coastal and Regional Ocean COmmunity model, covering the first 200 km from the coastline, and simulating the period 2006-2015. The biogeochemistry is represented by a simple, nitrogen-based, 4-component model (NPZD), since more complex options did not lead to improvement besides a considerable increase in the simulation time. The one-dimensional configuration uses the turbulent fields generated by the three-dimensional simulations and implements a novel Lagrangian biogeochemistry approach.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

The Southern Benguela is the meridional sector of the Eastern Benguela Upwelling System (EBUS), one of the major large marine ecosystems characterized by persistent conditions of nutrient-rich, deep-water upwelling and consequent high levels of primary and secondary production.

The following text is extracted from Fearon et al. (2023) the publication that describes the main results of the simulations. The seasonality in the wind forcing is governed by permanent but seasonally migrating subtropical high-pressure systems over the Atlantic and Pacific oceans, as well as land-based thermal low-pressure systems which develop to the east of the oceanic highs. As such, summer months are characterised by intensified alongshore equatorward winds, increased upwelling, and enhanced productivity, particularly at high latitudes. Eastward traveling midlatitude cyclones result in periodic weakening or abatement of the equatorward winds, setting up the upwelling-relaxation cycle through wind variability with a time-scale of days to weeks. Intensified equatorward winds drive the upwelling of nutrient-rich subsurface waters while wind relaxation of equatorward winds is important for the retention of upwelled nutrients, thereby sustaining primary productivity (Pitcher et al., 2014).

The Southern Benguela Upwelling System (SBUS) is one of the main regional targets of AtlantECO, with a focus on the study of changes in community structure driven by co-limiting environmental drivers and carbon export. The regional Southern Benguela simulations have been done with two different configurations of the CROCO numerical ocean model (Coastal and Regional Ocean COmmunity model, <http://www.croco-ocean.org>).

We notice that there are very few publications that have studied the Southern Benguela biogeochemical distribution and variability, despite the many papers published on other EBUS such as the California Current system. This is not for a lack of effort, but the majority of these work have not been published due to limited results.

This study has been assessed using data made available from the South African Department of Forestry Fisheries and the Environment, from the ESA Climate Change Initiative and from the EU Copernicus Marine Service. The specific DOIs are indicated in the text and references.

4 Models' Descriptions and Configurations

This section highlights the main features of the modelling systems used in the project: the three-dimensional CROCO model implementation and the one-dimensional Lagrangian biogeochemistry model.

CROCO is a three-dimensional terrain-following ocean model, which solves the primitive equations under the Boussinesq and hydrostatic approximations using finite difference numerical schemes (Shchepetkin and McWilliams, 2005; Deburu et al., 2012). All the simulations were performed with CROCO v1.0. The code and configurations are currently hosted on a gitlab instance of the University of Cape Town to avoid conflict with the official repository of CROCO. It is not expected to do further development on this version, and it should therefore be considered a frozen version for the AtlantECO project.

The *aquacosm* approach (Paparella and Vichi, 2020) implementation in the SBUS is still preliminary and will be introduced here for future references. We used both idealized simulations and also forced with results from the physical CROCO simulations.

4.1 CROCO Configurations

The complete description of the two ocean physics configurations is available in Fearon (2021), Fearon et al. (2022; 2023), and Dey and Vichi (2020). The next sections highlight the main features and introduce the biogeochemical model.

All configurations have been developed with CROCO-v1.0. They differ in terms of the domain and grid resolution:

- D01 - Realistically configured 2DV model of St Helena Bay (Fearon et al., 2022)
- D02 - Analytically configured 2DV model (Fearon, 2021)
- D03 - Southern Benguela AGRIF nesting: 3 km resolution parent (63x202x50), 1 km resolution child (98x242x50) (Figure 1, Fearon et al., 2023)
- D04 - Southern Benguela, 3 km resolution (102x202x50), no child domain (Figure 2, Dey and Vichi, 2020; Dey et al., 2021)

The simulations with the BGC model also have the keyword "B1", and they were only performed for the D04 configuration.

50 levels are used to define the vertical grid of all configurations, including the child domain. The bathymetry is a digital version of the most detailed available navigation charts for the region, as kindly provided by the Hydrographer of the South African Navy (this product is not publicly available and was used by concession of the SANHO). A baroclinic time-step of 6 min is adopted for the temporal integration of D04 and D03 parent domains and 2 min for the child domain. The model is initialized and forced at the lateral boundary conditions using the daily HYCOM ocean reanalysis data from the Global Ocean Forecasting System (GOFS) 3.1, obtained from the Naval Research Laboratory: Ocean Dynamics and Prediction Branch. The D03 nested configuration is forced with downscaled products from ERA-Interim obtained with the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model configuration developed by the Climate Systems Analysis Group (CSAG) at the University of Cape Town (Wind Atlas for South Africa, WASA, Lennard et al., 2015. See the data domain in Figure 2). The WASA model output is available on a 3 km horizontal resolution grid at hourly intervals for the period November 2005 to October 2013 (8 years). The D04 configuration was tested both with these higher resolution data, but the product used in AtlantECO was obtained using the 6-hourly Climate Forcing Reanalysis (CFSR) version 1 (available at 0.3° spatial resolution) and version 2 (0.2° spatial resolution) data to extend the simulation period to 10 years from 1 January 2006 to 31 December 2015.

Figure 1 Model grids for the nested configuration D03. From Fearon et al. (2023). The St. Helena Bay Monitoring Line is shown in the left panel.

Figure 2 Model domain for configuration D04 (from Dey and Uichi, 2020, depths in m). Configuration D04 is more extended than D03 to cover the Agulhas Bank region. The larger frame indicates the region where downscaled hourly wind data are available.

4.2 Biogeochemical model (BGC)

The SBUS was meant to be studied with a new coupling between CROCO and the BFM. Preliminary tests were conducted with both the standard BGC models available in CROCO, a simple NPZD (nutrient-phytoplankton-zooplankton-detritus) and the intermediate complexity model PISCES. These results indicated that the complexity of the BGC model did not improve on the main discrepancies observed in the simulation of bulk diagnostics such as the distribution of chlorophyll biomass and primary production (see Sec. 5.2). Given the

very good representation of the ocean physics, this was attributed to some deficiencies in the coupling between the physics and the BGC, and therefore the simpler NPZD BGC model was used throughout the project. The BFM is used in the Lagrangian simulations described in Sec. 4.3.

In the 4-component NPZD model, all the BGC variables are accounted in the unit of nitrogen concentration (mmol N m^{-3}). Nitrate is the only limiting nutrient. Chlorophyll and carbon concentrations are derived diagnostics, obtained from constant ratios. The initial and boundary conditions for nitrate were obtained from the WOA 2009. Initial and boundary phytoplankton and zooplankton distributions were constructed for the CROCO grid from the surface chl-a observation of ESA-CCI OC V4.2 and Glob-Colour (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00281>).

4.3 Aquacosm configurations

The 1D water column model was ideally located at point EB in Figure 1, with a water column depth of 50 m. The Eulerian model resolves the following equation for the time-varying vertical distribution of a generic biogeochemical tracer C:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\kappa(z, t) \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right) + \dot{C}.$$

where k is the turbulent diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), also a function of time and the vertical coordinate. The last term represents the biogeochemical reaction terms affecting the concentration of C.

Turbulent diffusivities are obtained from the idealized simulations described in Fearon et al. (2021) and from the output of the CROCO simulation over 7 days in March 2011. The numerical scheme for the Eulerian integrator is a second-order explicit method. The Lagrangian integrator and the theory of the aquacosm approach are fully described in Paparella and Vichi (2020, their section 2.4). The model resolves the eddy diffusivity-driven Brownian motion of individual Lagrangian parcels considered to be tiny control volumes. They should be thought of as minuscule aquatic mesocosms (aquacosm), which are carried by the ocean dynamics, and are homogeneous in their biogeochemical content(s). Aquacosms are not isolated and exchange mass between nearby aquacosms through irreversible mixing according to the relative concentration of each constituent. The coupling strength is controlled by a dimensional parameter (length in 1D, volume in 3D), which varies from 0 to ~ 1 mm, respectively representing isolated Lagrangian transport and the Eulerian simulations. For simplicity, all the experiments have been run with one single constituent representing chlorophyll concentration, and the co-limitation induced by turbulence and light have been explored.

The code is available at the following URL: <https://github.com/UCT-MARiS/aquacosm1D>

The biogeochemical reaction term is derived from the Biogeochemical Flux Model (BFM; Vichi et al., 2023). It resolves the carbon content of phytoplankton as affected by turbulence and light availability

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} &= \dot{C} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\kappa \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right) \\ \dot{C} &= r f^E C - \mu C - \frac{a C^2}{C_h + C} \\ f^E &= 1 - \exp \left(- \frac{\alpha E_{PAR}}{r} \theta_{chl} \right) \\ E_{PAR}(z) &= \varepsilon_{PAR} Q_s e^{-\lambda z} \end{aligned}$$

where C is the carbon concentration in mg m^{-3} and E_{PAR} is the vertical light distribution. The parameters are as follows:

θ_{chl} = chlorophyll/carbon = $C_{chl}/C = 0.017 \text{ mg Chl mg C}^{-1}$

r = maximum photosynthetic rate = 1 days^{-1}

λ = light decay = $1/5 \text{ m}^{-1}$

μ = respiration rate = 0.16 days^{-1}

C_h = crowding half saturation = 125 mg m^{-3}

α = crowding mortality = 0.65_{days}^{-1}
 Q_s = shortwave radiation = Daily variable $W m^{-2}$

5 Data description and analysis

5.1 SBUS physical model results

The model results are stored according to the standard CROCO output. The NetCDF files are divided into monthly files with daily outputs. The total volume of stored data is 0.5 TB. This volume is too big to be handled by the servers at the University of Cape Town, and due to policies constraints that were clarified only recently, the CMCC DDS that was used for distributing the Atlantic ocean simulations cannot be used. Data are therefore only available internally to the consortium and reduced output will be published with the relevant publications.

The model results have been validated against measurements made available by the South African Department of Forestry Fisheries and the Environment (Lamont et al., 2015). A climatology was computed from seasonal data collected along the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line (Figure 1) and compared with the model climatology.

Figure 3 Comparison of simulated ocean temperature climatology (D04 configuration) against data from the SHBML.

A 3-year time-series of measured daily averaged temperature at the Elands Bay fixed mooring ('EB' in Figure 1), was also compared with the model output, indicating the excellent performance of the simulation in the shallow coastal environment (detailed statistics are available in Fearon et al., 2023).

Figure 4 Time-series comparison of daily averaged measured and modelled temperature at 5 m and 20 m depths at the Elands Bay fixed mooring ('EB' in Figure 1), located in 20 m water depth). The stratification index is simply the difference between the temperatures. (D03 configuration; from Fearon et al., 2023).

The mean seasonal surface cycles of temperature and salinity are presented in, and compared with, the coarse resolution HYCOM model output that is used for the boundary conditions. The higher horizontal resolution and updated bottom topography improves on some of the biases observed in the reanalysis, notably the excessive surface cooling in the austral winter month and the low coastal salinity. Upwelling is also more intensified in the summer months in the D03 and D04 configurations and shows realistic changes at the sub-daily scale (Figure 6).

Figure 5 Seasonal sea surface climatologies of temperature (degrees C) and salinity (psu) for CROCO D04 and the HYCOM reanalysis used as boundary conditions. The spurious low-salinity signal in the reanalysis is removed in the CROCO simulation.

Figure 6 6-hourly snapshots of modelled SST and surface current vectors over an upwelling event, demonstrating the outcropping and subduction of the inner shelf upwelling. (from Fearon et al., 2023)

5.2 SBUS BGC simulations

The CROCO NPZD model for BGC was produced for the D04 configuration spanning the period 2006-2015. The seasonal cycle of model variables in nitrogen units are presented for the example Station 3 along the SHBML (Figure 7). The high temporal variability of the simulated physical fields are evident in the distribution of nitrate, which shows the upwelling to start from November/December and to continue over the austral summer months, with additional mixing events evident during the more stratified winter period. Nitrate is more depleted during winter also at depth, and the nutricline is closer to the surface between February and April, with some interesting re-stratification events such as the one seen at the beginning of March. Please note that the nutrient concentration surface values are not limiting during this spring-summer period. The plankton functional groups are active in the upper column above the pycnocline/nutricline, with evidence of responding to the surface mixing events. Organic matter export (DET variable in Figure 7) does not reach the bottom at this relatively shallow location, besides in January/February when plankton biomass is larger.

Mean surface fields (Figure 8) reveal two contrasting patterns between the processes of primary production and secondary consumption/remineralization. The former have sharper gradients that are still visible in the seasonal climatology with a depleted nutrient concentration in the southern sector, very close to the coast. There is also a clear footprint of the Cape Columbine jet revealed by the depleted phytoplankton concentration in winter/spring (July to November). It is unknown whether these processes are realistic since there are few data at sufficient temporal and spatial resolution away from the SHBML. Spatial gradients become more diffused when looking at the zooplankton and detritus variables, which spread offshore and result more homogeneously distributed.

Figure 7 Annual cycle at Station 3 in the SHBML for the BGC variables nitrate (NO₃), phytoplankton (PHYTO), zooplankton (ZOO), particulate organic detritus (DET) in mg N m⁻³, and chlorophyll (CHL, mg m⁻³).

Figure 8 Surface seasonal climatologies of BGC variables' concentration for nitrate, phytoplankton, zooplankton, and detritus (mg N m^{-3}) from the CROCO simulation.

The comparison was performed with satellite data from the ESA-CCI Ocean Colour (Sathyendranath et al., 2019, 2020) and from model output generated with the NEMO-PISCES hindcast simulation from CMEMS (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00019>). The annual chlorophyll concentration from CROCO is spatially homogenous (Figure 9a), with almost no offshore gradient besides in the region between Cape Peninsula and Cape Columbine. Satellite data show a progressive gradient from high chlorophyll close to the coast between 6 and 10 mg Chl m^{-3} and offshore concentrations lower than $0.4 \text{ mg Chl m}^{-3}$. A similar lack of gradient is simulated by the CMEMS product ($\sim 25 \text{ km}$ grid resolution, Figure 9c), indicating that the substantial increased resolution in CROCO does not improve the bias. There is a better simulation of the chlorophyll in the Agulhas-Benguela intersection region where CMEMS has no biomass (either for lack of growth or export), although the coastal band is too extended offshore.

When comparing the spatially averaged monthly timeseries separated into offshore and onshore regions (approximately masking data inside or outside 100 km from the coastline, respectively), we observe a major discrepancy between satellite observations and models (Figure 9). The coastal region shows a high background chlorophyll concentration of $\sim 5 \text{ mg Chl m}^{-3}$ with summer peaks and winter troughs which are not present in CROCO and in CMEMS. The models only simulate summer peaks and revert to the background offshore concentration in winter. Sharper fluctuations and higher interannual variability are observed with the higher resolution CROCO model with respect to CMEMS, which is connected to the better resolution and daily evolution of the physical fronts (see Sec. 5.1). Both models simulate well the observed offshore concentration, but extend these features to the coastal ocean, which shows higher, but still underestimated, biomass production only during the summer months. This discrepancy has to be attributed to the coupling between the biogeochemical model the physical model, since the excellent performance of the physical model indicates skill in the shallower area (Figure 6).

The biogeochemistry shows a realistic seasonal cycle in the vertical, but there is a complete lack of horizontal features in the nutrient and plankton biomass. We tested the role of zooplankton predation as an additional effective diffusivity term which may contribute to the horizontal smoothing of the biogeochemical variables. Figures 9 and 10 (panels d) present the results of a simulation with extremely reduced grazing, to assess the sensitivity of this component on the emergence of the phytoplankton coastal maxima. The results demonstrate that biomass is sensibly augmented but the horizontal gradient does not develop despite the source of nutrient being linked to the near-coastal upwelling. The diffused feature of the biogeochemistry is more likely to be connected to the inadequate coupling between the biogeochemical rates and the advective/turbulent transport. This conclusion is corroborated by the time series in the coastal and offshore regions (Figure 10c). There is an enhancement of the seasonality without the development of a more productive baseline in the coastal strip.

Figure 9 Climatological surface chlorophyll concentration (mg m^{-3}) from a) CROCO simulations, b) ocean colour data (ESA-CCI), c) CMEMS hindcast product GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_BIO_001_02, and d) the sensitivity simulation with reduced zooplankton predation.

Figure 10 Timeseries of average chlorophyll concentration (mg m^{-3}) from the model and data shown in Figure 9. The average is computed over the CROCO model domain and the mask approximately separates the first 100 km of the coastal band.

5.3 Aquacosc simulations

The first implementation of the aquacosc approach in the shallow SBUS system was done using the idealised model from Fearon et al. (2020). A horizontal pressure gradient interacts with the land-sea breeze to generate intermittent shear and turbulence. This model allows to observe the impact of patchiness on the vertical distribution of a passive tracer which is initialized to 1 beneath the mean thermocline (Figure 11).

The vertical diapycnal diffusivity generated by the shear stress leads to the presence of aquacosms with high concentration in the upper ocean and low concentration at depth. The coarse graining of the concentration in the individual parcels shows that the high-coupling mode reproduces the results of the Eulerian model, while the weak-coupling modifies the vertical distribution in a more realistic way similar to patches observed in the vertical profiles in the mixed layer (Figure 12a), and also diminishes the growth of the concentration in the upper layer due to the preservation of the double direction of the Lagrangian motion.

The results produced with the active biogeochemistry from the BFM are shown in Figure 13. The differences between the Eulerian and aquacosc simulations are smaller than in the previous passive case. The patchiness does modify the vertical profile of Chl in the mixed layer showing a few undulations, but the mean bulk biomass is similar in the upper layer. This is an expected results when the non-linearities in the reaction terms do not allow for the propagation of the patchiness. Preliminary results indicate that an increase of the light attenuation or of the crowding mortality parameter enhances the differences between the simulations as observed in Paparella and Vichi (2020).

Figure 11 Vertical distribution of a passive tracer initialized below the thermocline and affected by semi-diurnal shear turbulence. The results on the left are computed with a high coupling degree, compatible with a Eulerian approximation, while the results on the right use a coupling parameter that allows for patchiness.

Figure 12 Realistic and analytical initial conditions used in the simulations. Observations are from Lucas et al. (2014).

Figure 13 Same as in Figure 12 but for the realistic simulation

6 Conclusion

The physical simulations of the Southern Benguela have been completed demonstrating the importance of the high-resolution atmospheric forcing in establishing the sub-daily variability and the dynamical features of the frontal zone in this upwelling system. Such improvements are however not reflected in the biogeochemical simulations, which show smoothed gradients towards the shelf region, with major discrepancy in the coastal region where the biomass is much higher in the satellite observations. These are equivalent to the results from much coarser operational modelling products despite the physics of this configuration is notably performing better in the coastal strip.

The Lagrangian biogeochemical model based on the *aquacosm* approach has been successfully implemented and tested in the region in idealized and more realistic setups. The library is publicly available on GitHub and will be eventually linked to the AtlantECO Zenodo page once the manuscript is published.

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